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EXPLORING THE INTERPLAY BETWEEN CULTURE AND ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS

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Abstract

The role of culture in development of entrepreneurial intentions have get attention from the global researchers. Researchers applied the concept of regional, national and global culture for the development of attentions to start new venture. The intent of this work is to study impact of culture in determining the entrepreneurial intentions along the components of Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) among students. However, the population is students of business studies, enrolled in university degree programs and currently in 3rd or 4th year of their bachelor degree program and Master's degree program. In this work data collection procedure is adopted by using self-administrative questionnaire from the public and private universities of AJ&K state and Pakistan. The data collection is based upon contentious sampling techniques. Total 1100 questionnaires were distributed and total questionnaire

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900 questionnaires was received from which 874 questionnaires were able to use in current study. Data was analyzed by using SPSS. According to results, all the constructs of TPB indicate positive significant relationship on entrepreneurial intention. Also, result indicated, culture has played moderating role among the relationship of Components of TPB and entrepreneurship intention.

INTRODUCTION

EI is vital resource for the development of entrepreneurship (Bae, Qian & Fiet, 2014). Entrepreneurship research is becoming most popular in academia due to its contribution in overcoming the unemployment issues (Karami et al., 2024; Keat, Selvarajah & Meyer (2011), particularly in developing countries. It is the need of time for developing countries to generate more entrepreneurial activities which arises from entrepreneurial intentions (Yaghoubi Farani, Karimi & Motaghd 2017); Ataei, Karimi, & Zarei (2024) to overcome unemployment issues. Here is role of institutions to grow entrepreneurial intentions among students to strengthen the entrepreneurship and produce more entrepreneurial activities (Qureshi & Mian, 2021; Kelley, Singer & Herrington, 2012). Entrepreneurship is a set of planned behavior Fretschner (2014) and intention is a main cornerstone in individual behavior development (Bachmann et al., 2024). It is true in that case when it is challenging to observe the behavior of an individual in volatile time lag and exceptional cases (Carland & Carland, 1997). Entrepreneurial intention is primary and essential step toward the sequential process of starting new venture. So, definition of entrepreneurial intentions could be “the conscious state of mind that directs personal attention, experience, and behavior toward planned entrepreneurial behavior” Bird & West (1998). Our current study’s study is explores of TPB in determining the entrepreneurial intentions within students of business studies in Pakistan. Students are popular group of population in the research of entrepreneurial intentions (Valencia-Arias, Arango-Botero & Sánchez-Torres (2022).; Hattab, 2014) because they considered having a high capacity to become entrepreneur (Olsen, 2013). Accordingly, role of institutions in career counseling Hong, Song, & Yoo, (2013), age range (Neneh, 2019), and social economic background are most suitable features in defining the entrepreneurial intentions within students.

It is clearly deliberated in the TPB, an individual’s attitude towards behavior (ATB), subjective norms (SN) and Perceived behavior control (PBC) are main constructs in measuring entrepreneurial intentions. Simply, components of EI are applied to find, how tough to find that people are willing to try and of how much an

effort they are exerting to perform the behavior” (Ajzen, 1991). ATB “degree to which a person has a favorable or unfavorable evaluation or appraisal of the behavior in question”. It is also mentioned, an individual desire to be self-employed (Nicolaou, & Souitaris, 2016). Subjective Norms in TPB refer as “a Perceived social pressure to perform the action of being monitored” (Ajzen, 1991). The view of family, friends and other close people is influencing the career choice to become entrepreneur (Liñán & Chen, 2006). Perceived Behavior Control (PBC) denotes “the perception of the easiness or difficult fulfillment of the behavior of interest” this concept of PBC is matched with concept of self-efficiency (Campo 2010). Several studies are held to support TPB about outcome of entrepreneurial intentions (Díaz-García ,2010). But few research findings suggest that attitude toward behavior do not influence entrepreneurial intentions (Zhang, Wang, & Owen, 2015; Siu & Lo, 2013). So, results are not reliable in the research of Ruiz *et al.* (2017). Consequently, with the different views on entrepreneurial intentions, we need to explore further research on the components of TPB.

However, Fayolle and Linan, (2014) have brought entrepreneurial intentions into new life again by identifying the new possible way of research. For example, they argue that for better understanding of entrepreneurial intentions we need to integrate it with other theories and methodologies like mediation effects and (moderation). So, in current research we are studying antecedents of TPB with culture as a moderator. According to Theory of Planned Behavior, Cultural values will affect on the motivational antecedents of TPB (Linan, & Chen, 2009). Cultural dimensions (Hofstede *et al.* 2001), collectivism, individualism, power distance and uncertainty avoidance are very important in understanding the EIs among undergraduates (Morris *et al.* 2017). National culture considered valuable in examining the EIs among students and cultural dimensions serve as moderator to influence the other factors to make the Intentions (Morris *et al.* 2017). These constructs of TPB are influenced by value of culture. So, culture is the concept of “collective programming of the mind that distinguishes the members of one group or category of people from another” (Hofstede *et al.* 2001). Moreover, Krueger, Reilly & Carsrud (2000). explains that entrepreneurial intention is rooted in cultural and societal context. So, it is very important to find out cultural effect on the antecedents of entrepreneurial intentions to shape new way to entrepreneurial intentions.

Literature Review

The research literature in entrepreneurial intentions has increased over the years. Several researchers are continuously backing the research in the field of EIs. There are two research models that dominate in the literature of entrepreneurship intentions. One is “Theory of Planned (TPB)” by Ajzen (1991) and second is “Entrepreneurial Event Model (EEM)” by Shapero and Sokol (1982). TPB has been explained three factors, Attitude Toward Behavior (ATB), Subjective Norms (SN) and Perceived Behavior Control (PBC). Although, Entrepreneurial Event Model (EEM) has been explained, Perceived Feasibility (PF), Perceived Desirability

(PD) and Propensity to Act (PA) for determining EIs among students. However, Kruger, Reilly and Carsrud (2000) have tested both the model and regard both the models are overlapping to their components of EIs. Accordingly, both the models have strong empirical provisions but in entrepreneurship studies TPB has been revealed as robust theory in examining the entrepreneurial intentions (Kolvereid. 1997; Valencia *et al.* 2015. The TPB has been used in many fields comprehensively and most researchers dedicated their time to test the TPB (Paul & Shrivastava, (2016); Shook, Priem, & McGee, (2003); Fayolle, Gailly & Lassas- Clerc, (2006). This Entrepreneurial intention model is applicable in examining the behavior and intentions, particularly in career related studies (Krueger, 1993).

Potishuk & Kratzer (2017) find the impact of entrepreneurial attitude on entrepreneurial intentions with help of TPB. Their findings indicate a substantial effect on attitude toward EIs. They argued that Attitude Toward entrepreneurship has robust influence on EIs, and it is more relevant to increasing the EI. Several empirical studies established strong link between entrepreneurial attitudes and entrepreneurial intentions.

Most studies shows an insignificant impact of Subjective Norms (SN) on EIs (Autio, 2011). However, few studies institute very weak link between entrepreneurial intentions and subjective norms (Armitage, & Conner, 2001). Our social contacts influence entrepreneurial intentions which may stimulate what we are expecting from others. An individual inclined toward the entrepreneur's decision when they feel that referenced people would support his decision (Linan, & Santos, 2007). Roy, Akhtar and Das (2017), applied the TPB in finding the EIs by using SEM technique. Findings of their studies suggested that Attitude Toward entrepreneurship has a substantial positive relationship while subjective norms (SN) have significant but weak relationships. Joseph (2024) also argued that social Norms influenced the entrepreneurial intentions among students. But Zheng, (2010) have found negative relationship between EIs and Subjective Norms.

PBC is very important in entrepreneurship research, to control the obstacles regarding resources in that type of environment where entrepreneurial activities are operating make to control them previously. Several studies highlighted that ATB and PBC predict positive substantial impact on entrepreneurial intentions, but social norms showed insignificant impact on entrepreneurial intentions (Lina, & Chen, 2009). However, some studies indicated PBC and SN is very important in determining the entrepreneurial intentions (Malebana & Swanepoel 2014). SN have greater influence on EIs (Kautonen *et al.* 2015). However, Linan *et al.* (2011); Lee (2024); Linan and Santos (2007) did not find the significant impact of subjective norms on EI. Therefore, based on this related work on Entrepreneurial intentions, we can hypothesize as follows:

H₁: Attitude toward Behavior (ATB) affects EIs among students of Business studies

H₂: Subjective Norms (SN) affect EIs among students of Business Studies

H₃: Perceived Behavior Control (PBC) effect the EIs among students of Business Studies.

Moderating Role of Culture

Moreover, some researchers had debated that TPB is most suitable theory to understand impact of other constructs on entrepreneurial intentions (Paul & Shrivastava 2016; Krueger & Carsrud 1993). Based on this assumption, we study the culture with ATB, SN and PBC. To study the TPB on students at Pakistani universities is due to strong empirical support of TPB for determining EIs. The empirical consequences of previous research indicate that culture moderates relationship between EIs and its components (Engle, Schlaegel & Delanoe 2011). Culture help to determine whether entrepreneurial activities in a society are striking or not.

Similarly, TPB is strong interpreter of EIs among students in developing countries as compared to developed countries (Zeb, 2022; Paul, Hermel & Srivatava, 2017). Engle *et al.* (2010), studied entrepreneurial intentions in diverse countries and found that only one element (Subjective Norms) of TPB is significant in predicting the entrepreneurial in each country's intentions. Moreover, according to Lakovleva *et al.* (2011), determine EI by applying TPB in both developed and developing countries. According to their conclusion, antecedents of TPB has high scores into developing countries as compared to developed countries. Hence, lot of studies has been conducted on the TPB linked with national culture, economic growth and entrepreneurial intentions (Zeb, ASajid,& Iqbal (2019). For understanding the effect of culture with components of TPB is very important to refine the knowledge of entrepreneurship (Cacciotti & Hayton 2013). The main task of present work is to recognize significant effect of antecedents of TPB (Kautonen et al., 2015) with linking the culture.

H₄: Culture Moderate the relationship between antecedents of TPB and Eis.

Figure 1: Research Model

Methodology

In current study, we used students of business studies from higher education institutions of Pakistan as sample to find the entrepreneurial intentions. The self-administered questionnaire method used for data collection related to the components of EIs and culture. A scale from the study of Luthje & Franke (2003) and Kreueger et al. (2000) have been used in this research. Similarly, Perceived Behavior Control and subjective norms have been measured by using the scale of Autio (2011).

To find the impact of culture on EIs, Sternberg (2004) scale related to ATB and PBC have six items. Similarly, SN has four items scale of measurement, and twenty-five items have been used to measure culture construct.

Table: 1a Reliability Analysis

Variables	Number of Items	Cronbach's α
1. Entrepreneur Intentions	06	0.814
2. Attitude towards Entrepreneurship	06	0.847
3. Subjective Norms	04	0.688
4. Perceived Behaviour Control	06	0.877
5. Culture	25	0.707

Table 1b refers to explaining the minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation values of study variables. According to given table there are 874 observations to analyze the detailed description of variables. EA is "Attitude towards Entrepreneurship" having 874 number of observations. The mean value of EA is 3.944 which shows the average value of respondents. The minimum and maximum value of EA is 1 and 5. The SD is 0.7291. Likewise, SN is subjective norms, and their number of observations is 874. The minimum level of measurement is 1 and maximum level of measurement is 5. The mean value of SN is 3.810 and SD is 0.8430. PBC refers to Perceived Behavior control. The number of observations is 874. Culture and EI having 874 respondents. The min. and max. values of Culture and EI are (1 and 5). The mean values of both variables are (3.462 & 0.4902). Gender has 874 observations. The minimum level of measurement is 1 and maximum level of measurement is 2. The mean level valued at 1.355 and SD is 0.4790. Age is demographic character, and its minimum level valued at 1 and maximum level valued 4. The mean reading is valued at 2.707 and SD is 0.9138.

Table 1b: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
EA	874	1.00	5.00	3.944	.7291
SN	874	1.00	5.00	3.810	.8430
PBC	874	1.00	5.00	3.460	1.0471
Culture	874	1.00	5.00	3.462	.4902
EI	874	1.00	5.00	4.034	.6997
Gender	874	1.00	2.00	1.355	.4790
Age	874	1.00	4.00	2.707	.9138
US	874	1.00	2.00	1.489	.5001
Education	874	1.00	4.00	2.836	.7287

EA "Attitude towards Entrepreneurship", SN "Subjective Norms", PBC "Perceived behaviour control", EI "Entrepreneur Intentions", US "Uni- Status".

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

	EA	SN	PBC	Culture	EI
EA	1				
SN	.248**	1			
PBC	.484**	.168**	1		
Culture	.053	.028	-.023	1	

EI	.506**	.252**	.277**	.407**	1
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*P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0.00001, EA “Attitude towards Entrepreneurship”, SN “Subjective Norms”, PBC “Perceived behavior control”, EI “Entrepreneur Intentions”

Table number 2 explains correlation matrix of study variables. EA “Attitude towards Entrepreneurship” has significant relationship with SN with correlation value .248. The level of significance is 0.01, which shows the relationship is most significant. Likewise, EA “Attitude towards Entrepreneurship” has significant association with PBC and EI and correlation values are 0.484 and 0.506 and the level of significant is 0.01 that refers to high level of significant. Similarly, significant relationship exists between PBC and EI with correlation value .277 and significant level is 0.01. Similarly, subject norms and EI have positive and significant relationships with each other and correlation value is 0.252 and level of significant is 0.01.

Table 3: Regression Analysis (Direct effect)

Dependent Variable

Entrepreneur Intentions (EI)

Independent Variables	B	R ²	ΔR ²	SIG.
EA	0.485	0.256	0.255	0.00001
SN	0.112	0.273	0.271	0.00001
PBC	0.195	0.076	0.075	0.00001
Culture	0.581	0.166	0.165	0.00001

EA “Attitude towards Entrepreneurship”, SN “Subjective Norms”, PBC “Perceived behaviour control”, EI “Entrepreneur Intentions

Table number 3 refers to the regression analysis of study variables and table shows the dependent variable is Entrepreneur Intentions and Independent Variables EA, SN PBC and Culture. According to this regression table EA “Attitude towards Entrepreneurship” has significant effect on Entrepreneur Intentions ($\beta = .485$, $p > 0.0001$). The value of R^2 and ΔR^2 is 0.256 and 0.255 respectively. Similarly, SN “Subjective norms” has significant effect on EI “Entrepreneur Intention” ($\beta = .112$, $p > 0.0001$). The value of R^2 is 0.273 and the value of ΔR^2 is 0.271. According to table 4.3, PBC has significant effect with EI ($\beta = .195$,

$p > 0.0001$). The value of R^2 is 0.076 and the value of adjusted R^2 is 0.075. Likewise, culture has significant effect on EI ($\beta = .581$, $p > 0.0001$). The value of R^2 is 0.166 and the value of adjusted R^2 is 0.165.

Table 4: Moderation Analysis
Dependent Variable

Independent Variables	Entrepreneur Intentions (EI)			
	B	R ²	ΔR^2	SIG.
INT1	0.133	0.373	0.372	0.00001
INT2	0.081	0.169	0.168	0.00001
INT3	0.067	0.151	0.150	0.00001

EA "Attitude towards Entrepreneurship", SN "Subjective Norms", PBC "Perceived behavior control", EI "Entrepreneur Intentions, INT1 "EA*culture", INT2 "SN*culture", INT3 "PBC*culture" Table 4 refers to analyzing the moderation effects of study variables. In current study culture is using as moderation among the variables EA, PBC, SN and EI. According to given result INT1 refers to interaction term of EA*culture. According to INT1, there is a significant effect exist among interaction term and EIs. According to this result, the culture variable influences the relationship of EA and Entrepreneur intentions ($\beta = 0.133$, $p > 0.0001$). Similarly, INT2 refers to the interaction term between SN*culture. So, the results indicated that culture also influences the relationship of subjective norms and Entrepreneur intentions ($\beta = 0.081$, $p > 0.0001$). in this table, INT3 is refers to the interaction term of PBC*culture.it is clear from relationship that the culture influences the relationship PBC and Entrepreneur Intentions ($\beta = 0.067$, $p > 0.0001$).

Discussion and Conclusion

This study explores Entrepreneurship intention along with Attitude Towards Entrepreneurship, Subjective Norms (SN) and Perceived Behavior Control (PBC). However, in this study we measure the moderating effect of Culture among study variables. The current study uses the quantitative approach to collecting data. The current study collects the questionnaire from the Business graduates. In the light of results gain from collected data, current study explained the results of analyzed data. According to the first hypothesis "H₁" Attitude toward Behavior effect the Entrepreneurial Intentions within

students of Business studies. The results show that there is a significant effect of Attitude toward behavior toward EIs. TPB explained motivational factors. Krueger (1993), Entrepreneurial intention models are applicable in examining behavior and intentions, particularly in career related studies.

The hypothesis "H₂" is that Subjective Norms (SN) effect the Entrepreneurial Intentions among students of Business Studies. The results reported that subjective norms positively affect the entrepreneurship intentions. The result indicated that in Pakistan, ethical values and norms are strongly supported the business students to go for business and they encourage the business studies to leads the youngsters to become an entrepreneur. Roy, Akhtar and Das (2017), applied the TPB find EIs by using SEM technique and reported that SN has significant effect with entrepreneurship intentions. Results of "hypothesis H3" reported that PBC has significant relationship with EIs among students of Business Studies. Several studies highlighted that perceived behavior control predict positive significant impact on EIs (Robledo *et al.* 2015). Similarly, culture has positive impact on entrepreneurship intentions. It means Pakistani culture has positively support the business studies to promote the business hubs and encourage the students of business studies to start their own business and become a part of business community. According to H₄ results, culture has influenced TPB components on entrepreneurship intentions. The previous research indicate that national culture moderates the connection of entrepreneurial intentions and its components (Engle *et al.* 2010) it is stated that to understand about the effect of culture with components of TPB is very important to refine the knowledge of entrepreneurship.

Recommendations

Despite all efforts we have put in this study to find the entrepreneurial intentions within students, this study has some limitations. Firstly, the closed structural questionnaire used in this study makes it impossible to explore casual relationships but mostly in cases when study is cross sectional. We proposed that attitude, SN and PBC regulate the EIs. But this relationship can be vice versa for what factors would be considered in determining the entrepreneurial intention to create the new venture. So, it is recommended that a longitudinal study could be carried out to find this relationship. Similarly, it would be interesting to analyze the impact of control variables (status of institutions, age, sex) on entrepreneurial intentions. Despite all efforts we have to find the EIs among students but there are some limitations.

Upcoming studies should analyze journey from attitude of students to entrepreneurship to action in creating new ventures by considering the role of behavioral characteristics. Future research should sample from other disciplines instead of business graduates to find effect of behavioral factors on entrepreneurial intentions. In this study risk taking propensity did not support the previous literature findings. So, in future studies need to study further to check the true impact of risk-taking propensity on intentions of startup.

The data have been collected from university students regarding personality traits, culture, education and gender but the other environmental factors such as financial assistance and role model can also influence entrepreneurial intentions. So future researchers can used these factors with theory of planned to find entrepreneurial intentions. Lastly, universities and policy makers can select the students with the profile of entrepreneurial skills.

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